

Development of drag, lift, and torque models for cylindrical biomass particles in suspension systems

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ABSTRACT: The motion of non-spherical particles is widely encountered in suspension systems on heat and mass transfer for energy, chemical, and environmental engineering. However, the existing force models apply the assumptions of spherical or simplified particle geometries, making them insufficient for accurately describing the hydrodynamic behaviors of typical biomass particles like cylindrical straws in industrial co-firing settings. To address this limitation, this study employs an immersed boundary method particle-resolved direct numerical simulation (IBM-PR-DNS) to investigate the hydrodynamic forces acting on cylindrical particles with an aspect ratio of 2.5. A comprehensive analysis is conducted over a range of Reynolds numbers ($10 \leq Re \leq 2000$), solid volume fractions ($0.05 \leq \varphi \leq 0.2$), and particle incidence angles ($0^\circ \leq \theta \leq 90^\circ$). The results reveal that increasing

24 Reynolds number and solid volume fraction greatly enhance the complexity and heterogeneity of
25 local flow structures, resulting in pronounced non-uniformity in particle scale forces. The drag shows
26 a strong dependence on the incident angle, particularly at high Reynolds numbers, with a reduction
27 of up to 46.33% as θ increases from 5° to 85° . The lift and torque exhibit peak values near $\theta=45^\circ$,
28 and their magnitude increases with Re and ϕ due to intensified wake asymmetry and flow disturbances.
29 Based on extensive data, the correlations for the drag, lift, and torque are developed using a genetic
30 algorithm optimization framework. These models explicitly incorporate the effects of Reynolds
31 number, solid volume fraction, and incident angle, and well indicate agreement with the IBM-PR-
32 DNS results, with root mean square errors below 0.5. Compared to the existing correlations for
33 ellipsoids; disks; and cubes, the proposed models demonstrate better accuracy and robustness for
34 randomly oriented cylindrical biomass particles in the dense suspensions. This work might provide
35 reliable generalized force models for cylindrical particles in multiphase flows, and offer a high-
36 fidelity reference for numerical simulations of biomass co-firing, fluidized bed combustion, and
37 related gas-solid flow systems.

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39 **KEY WORDS:** Biomass; non-spherical particles; drag, lift and torque; suspension; solid volume
40 fractions.

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44 Nomenclature

Ar	Aspect ratio
A^*	Cross-sectional area of equivalent sphere $A^* = \pi D_{eq}^2 / 4$
a, b, c, r, t	Constants
CNN	Convolutional neural networks
C_D, C_L, C_T	Drag coefficient, Lift coefficient, Torque coefficient
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
D_{eq}	Equivalent-volume diameter
F_D, F_L, F_T	Drag force, Lift force, Torque
GA	Genetic algorithm
IBM	Immersed boundary method
LBM	Lattice Boltzmann method
p	Pressure
PR-DNS	Particle-resolved direct numerical simulation
Re	Reynolds number
R^2	Coefficient of determination
RMSE	Root mean square error
SDF	Signed distance function
$ \overline{u_f} - \overline{u_p} $	Relative velocity between the fluid $\overline{u_f}$ and particle $\overline{u_p}$
V_p	Particles volume
t	Time
Φ	Sphericity
θ	Incidence angles
φ	Solid volume fraction
ρ_f	Fluid density
μ_f	Dynamic viscosity

45 **1. Introduction**

46 In recent years, the application of non-spherical particles in multiphase reaction processes has
47 attracted increasing attention, particularly due to their significant role in heat and mass transfer
48 mechanisms[1-4]. The environmental impacts and carbon emissions associated with fossil fuel
49 consumption have led to increasing interest in co-firing biomass in coal-fired boilers as an effective
50 emission reduction strategy [5, 6]. Biomass is considered a carbon-neutral fuel and its integration into
51 coal-fired power plants not only helps to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, but also reduces
52 dependence on coal while increasing the share of renewable energy in the energy mix [7]. Currently,
53 suspension combustion - where the fuel is finely ground and injected into the furnace - is receiving
54 increasing attention in biomass power generation and co-firing applications [8]. However, this type
55 of combustion imposes strict requirements on fuel quality and particle size. Biomass must be
56 sufficiently pulverised to ensure efficient ignition and burnout performance [9]. Larger biomass
57 particles tend to cause incomplete combustion and reduce flame stability, especially at high blending
58 ratios or when burning only biomass. To overcome this, modifications to the combustion system or
59 pre-treatment of the biomass fuel are often required to meet operational requirements [10].

60 Compared with traditional pulverized coal, biomass particles exhibit highlight differences in
61 both physical properties and morphological characteristics [11]. Pulverized coal highlight forms
62 nearly spherical particles with small diameters on the order of tens of micrometers after milling. In
63 contrast, agricultural residues such as straw naturally possess fibrous structures, and upon simple
64 mechanical crushing, form cylindrical or rod-like particles with relatively larger diameters, often
65 reaching the millimeter scale [12], as illustrated in Fig. 1. Most existing Computational Fluid
66 Dynamic (CFD) boiler simulation tools are based on near spherical, very small pulverised coal
67 particle models. This makes it difficult to accurately capture the motion of large biomass particles.

68 Studies have shown that for large non-spherical biomass particles, the accuracy of conventional force
69 models declines sharply, even when basic shape factor corrections are applied. In particular, when
70 the equivalent-volume diameter (D_{eq}) of a particle exceeds approximately 3 millimeters, drag force
71 models based on shape factors exhibit rapidly increasing errors, resulting in highlight deviations in
72 the prediction of unburned carbon compared to experimental data [13]. This highlights the necessity
73 of incorporating the accurate geometry of biomass particles into the CFD models to avoid
74 considerable discrepancies in force prediction and trajectory estimation, which are essential for
75 evaluating combustion performance and pollutant formation. Non-spherical biomass particles also
76 experience more complex aerodynamic forces than their spherical counterparts. In addition to the
77 conventional drag force (F_D), the asymmetric geometry can induce highlight lift forces (F_L) and fluid-
78 induced torques (F_T), causing the particles to follow different trajectories and exhibit distinct
79 orientation dynamics. These differences directly influence the residence time, migration path, and
80 mixing efficiency of biomass particles with the surrounding flow, ultimately affecting the combustion
81 efficiency and emission [14]. Therefore, accurately capturing the dynamics of non-spherical biomass
82 particles—particularly drag, lift, and torque—is critical in CFD simulations [15, 16]. A
83 comprehensive understanding of these force components is essential for developing robust particle
84 motion models and improving the accuracy of multiphase flow and combustion simulations in
85 biomass-fired or co-firing boiler systems [7].

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Fig. 1 Representative particle samples used in co-firing: (a) raw pulverized coal; (b) near-spherical coal particle; (c) micrometer scale of coal; (d) crushed natural straw; (e) cylindrical straw biomass particles, and (f) millimeter scale of biomass.

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The hydrodynamics of non-spherical particles has long been a critical topic in multiphase flow research. Traditional studies have primarily focused on spherical particles, owing to their geometric simplicity and the ease of experimental and numerical implementation. As a result, the drag behavior of single spheres in various flow regimes has been extensively investigated, and empirical correlations covering a wide Reynolds number (Re) range have been developed [17-21]. In contrast, the report on non-spherical particles such as biomass has emerged more recently. The early approaches often relied on concepts such as equivalent-volume diameter and shape factors to approximate non-spherical particles as spheres, but these simplifications could not accurately capture shape-induced force differences. A classical example is the correlation by Haider and Levenspiel [22], which incorporates sphericity (Φ) to adjust the drag coefficient (C_D). However, such empirical formulas are typically based on limited datasets and do not explicitly account for particle orientation or high-Reynolds-number effects. Ganser [23] proposed a model combining distinct shape factors for Stokes and Newtonian regimes, which extended the Reynolds number applicability but still suffered

103 from limited accuracy, particularly for particles with large shape deviations from a sphere. Hölzer
104 and Sommerfeld [24, 25] developed a more general drag coefficient correlation using particle shape
105 descriptors such as sphericity, which performed well for a variety of shapes at low to moderate
106 Reynolds numbers. This model has been widely adopted in Euler–Lagrange multiphase simulations.
107 However, the later studies revealed that it could overpredict drag coefficient for extreme shapes or
108 specific orientations. For instance, Cao and Tafti [26] demonstrated through direct numerical
109 simulations that the Hölzer and Sommerfeld model highlight overestimates drag when flat cylindrical
110 particles face the flow at incidence angles $\theta=0^\circ$. Unlike the drag, the lift and torque on non-spherical
111 particles have received little attention. In theory, spherical particles experience no lift or steady torque
112 in uniform flows. However, asymmetric non-spherical particles at nonzero incidence angles may
113 experience both lateral lift forces and rotational torques. Zastawny et al. [27] derived correlations for
114 lift and torque coefficients of ellipsoidal particles at arbitrary orientations based on direct numerical
115 simulations, covering a moderate Reynolds number range. Ouchene et al. [28] extended the work to
116 flat non-spherical particles, enriching the dataset on orientation-dependent forces. Fröhlich et al.[29]
117 space even performed approximately 4400 high-resolution simulations to investigate the force
118 conditions of ellipsoidal particles in the range of Reynolds number $1 \leq Re \leq 100$, aspect ratio $1 \leq Ar \leq 8$,
119 and incidence angles $0^\circ \leq \theta \leq 90^\circ$, and derived highly accurate and widely applicable correlations of
120 drag, lift, and torque. In our previous work, Wang et al. [30-32] performed a series of particle-resolved
121 direct numerical simulations (PR-DNS) focused on cylindrical particles. Initial studies at an aspect
122 ratio $Ar=9$ yielded drag, lift, and torque data over $Re \leq 2000$ and $0^\circ \leq \theta \leq 90^\circ$, forming the basis for
123 preliminary correlations. This was extended to a broader range $6 \leq Ar \leq 22$, and functional relationships
124 were derived for the force coefficients as functions of Re , θ , and Ar . Latest studies, the parameter
125 space was further expanded to $1 \leq Re \leq 4000$, $1 \leq Ar \leq 30$, with convolutional neural networks (CNN)

126 used to enhance fitting accuracy and produce highly reliable predictions across a wide range of
127 conditions. It is worth noting that most of these studies still assume isolated particles, without
128 accounting for the influence of neighboring particles on the surrounding flow field.

129 In practical operating conditions, the particles do not exist in isolation. The local solid volume
130 fraction (ϕ), defined as the fraction of volume occupied by particles in a given region, has a substantial
131 impact on the fluid forces acting on the individual particle. However, most studies on particle
132 hydrodynamics were conducted under the assumption of negligible particle–particle interactions, i.e.,
133 the particles were assumed to be sufficiently far apart to not influence each other. In recent years,
134 increasing attention has been given to this limitation, and research has gradually emerged to address
135 the effects of solid volume fraction on non-spherical particle behavior [33-35]. When non-spherical
136 particles are suspended in a fluid at finite volume fractions, collective effects can highlight alter the
137 hydrodynamic forces acting on each particle. For spherical particles, well-established empirical
138 correlations exist to describe how drag rises with increasing ϕ , such as the models proposed by Ergun
139 [36], Wen and Yu [37], and Felice [38], as well as the more generalized formulation by Tenneti et al.
140 [39]. However, these models were developed based on experiments or simulations involving spherical
141 particles and cannot be directly applied to non-spherical systems. He et al. [40] were among the first
142 to study the momentum transfer of randomly distributed fixed ellipsoidal particles using PR-DNS.
143 They found that under moderate Reynolds numbers ($10 \leq Re \leq 200$), the drag on ellipsoidal particles
144 could differ by up to 35% compared to equivalent-volume spheres. Building on this, He and Tafti
145 [41] conducted detailed PR-DNS studies on ellipsoidal suspensions with $0.1 \leq \phi \leq 0.35$, analyzing the
146 variations in drag, lift, and torque under different Re , ϕ , and θ . Their findings showed large
147 fluctuations in particle forces, which became more pronounced at higher Reynolds numbers. Refs.
148 [42-44] extended this the work by systematically investigating elongated ellipsoids ($Ar=5$ and 10) at

149 $0.1 \leq \phi \leq 0.3$ under random orientations. Their results demonstrated that using isolated-particle drag
150 models combined with ϕ -based corrections derived leads to large errors for non-spherical particles.
151 To address this, they proposed a drag correlation that explicitly incorporates Re , ϕ , Ar , and θ .
152 Furthermore, an orientation order parameter was introduced to quantify the collective alignment of
153 ellipsoids in suspension, simplifying the estimation of average drag [43]. In addition to elongated
154 ellipsoids, other particle shapes have also been examined. For instance, Cao and Tafti [44] studied
155 flat cylindrical (disk-like) particles with $Ar=0.25$ and found that the drag follows a sinusoidal function
156 of θ across the ranges $10 \leq Re \leq 300$ and $0.1 \leq \phi \leq 0.3$. Rong et al. [45] developed correction terms for
157 ellipsoids with $0.25 \leq Ar \leq 4$ in packed beds. Chen and Müller [46] focused on cubic particles using the
158 Lattice Boltzmann Method (LBM), calculating drag forces in the ranges $Re \leq 200$ and $0.1 \leq \phi \leq 0.45$, and
159 proposed a Re and ϕ dependent drag correlation to improve accuracy in multiphase flow simulations.
160 However, most of these studies did not explicitly incorporate the influence of particle θ . More recently,
161 machine learning methods have been explored to model the complex force relationships of non-
162 spherical particles. For example, Ashwin et al. [47] applied deep learning techniques to predict the
163 drag on ellipsoidal particles in suspension for use in Euler–Lagrange or Euler–Euler simulations.
164 While such models can handle high-dimensional inputs, they often lack physical interpretability and
165 generalizability, and require large training datasets, which limits their practical application in
166 engineering contexts [47-49].

167 Despite the highlight progress made in the study of drag in non-spherical particle suspension
168 systems, as summarized in Table 1, several key challenges remain unresolved. First, the behavior of
169 lift and torque acting on non-spherical particles in suspension systems is still not well understood.
170 While numerous studies have focused on drag force correlations, comprehensive modeling of lift and
171 rotational torque remains limited. Second, most existing research has been conducted on particles with

172 specific aspect ratios, such as elongated ellipsoids with $Ar=5$ or $Ar=10$, or flat disk-like particles with
173 $Ar=0.25$. However, in biomass co-firing applications, cylindrical particles with moderate aspect ratios
174 (e.g., $Ar\approx 2.5$) are more representative of the actual morphology of milled agricultural residues.
175 Previous experimental studies on particle size distributions and shape characterizations of biomass
176 fuels such as wheat straw and rice straw have shown that naturally ground straw particles typically
177 exhibit aspect ratios ranging between 2.0 and 3.0, due to their inherent fibrous structure and
178 mechanical fragmentation characteristics during milling[10, 50, 51]. Therefore, selecting $Ar=2.5$ as
179 the basis for force correlation development in this study provides a statistically representative and
180 practically relevant geometric configuration for modeling biomass particles in industrial co-firing
181 conditions. To date, there is a lack of dedicated studies providing complete force correlations—
182 including drag, lift, and torque—for such particle geometries. Although general-purpose models can
183 be interpolated or extrapolated to estimate these forces, their accuracy for this class of particles
184 remains unverified. Lastly, due to the computational cost of PR-DNS, most studies have been
185 restricted to low or moderate Reynolds numbers (typically $Re\leq 300$). However, under practical
186 operating conditions in large coal-fired boiler hearths, millimeter-scale biomass particles may
187 experience flow regimes with Reynolds numbers as high as 2000 [30], far beyond the validated range
188 of existing models. This limits the applicability of current correlations in realistic engineering
189 scenarios and highlights the need for model extensions to higher Reynolds number regimes.

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191 Table 1 Drag correlations for particle suspension systems in the literatures

Authors	Correlation	Applicability
Hölzer and Sommerfeld[25]	$C_D = \frac{8}{Re} \frac{1}{\psi_{\square}^{1/2}} + \frac{16}{Re} \frac{1}{\psi^{1/2}} + \frac{3}{Re} \frac{1}{\psi^{3/4}} + 0.421^{0.4(-\log\psi)^{0.2}} \frac{1}{\psi_{\perp}}$ $F_{D0} = \frac{1}{2} \rho_f u_f C_D \frac{\pi D_{eq}^2}{4}$	Single particle in the flow field arbitrary geometry

Felice[38]	$F_D = F_{D0}\varepsilon^{-\gamma}, \quad \varepsilon = 1 - \varphi$ $\gamma = 3.7 - 0.65 \exp[-0.5(1.5 - \log Re)^2]$	Packed beds of spherical particles
Tenneti et al.[39]	$F_D = \frac{F_{D0}}{(1-\varphi)^3} + A + \varphi^3 Re(0.95 + \frac{0.61\varphi^3}{(1-\varphi)^2})$ $A = \frac{5.81\varphi}{(1-\varphi)^3} + 0.48 + \frac{0.61\varphi^{1/3}}{(1-\varphi)^4}$	$0.01 \leq Re \leq 300$ $0.1 \leq \varphi \leq 0.5$ Spherical particle suspensions.
Rong et al.[45]	$F_D = F_{D0}\varepsilon^{-\beta-\lambda}, \quad \varepsilon = 1 - \varphi$ $\beta = 2.65(\varepsilon + 1) - (5.3 - 3.5\varepsilon)\varepsilon^2 \exp[-0.5(1.5 - \log Re)^2]$ $\lambda = (1 - \psi)(g - f \exp[-0.5(1.5 - \log Re)^2])$ $g = 39\psi - 20.6$ $f = 101.8(\psi - 0.81)^2 + 2.4$	$0.25 \leq Ar \leq 4$ Packed beds of ellipidst
Chen and Müller[46]	$F_D = \frac{10\varphi}{(1-\varphi)^2} + (1-\varphi)^{0.5}(-0.2 + 5.6\varphi^{0.5}) + L$ $L = \frac{-1.17(1-\varphi)^{-1} + 0.45\varphi(1-\varphi) + 8.4Re^{-0.15+0.24\varphi}}{1 + 10^{2\varphi} Re^{(-0.5-2\varphi)}}$	$Re \leq 200$ $0.1 \leq \varphi \leq 0.45$ Cubic particles
Cao and Tafti[44]	$F_{D,\theta} = F_{D,\theta=0^\circ} + (F_{D,\theta=90^\circ} - F_{D,\theta=0^\circ})\sin\theta$ $F_{D,\theta=0^\circ} = (a_1 Re^{b_1} + c_1(1-\varphi))(1-\varphi)^{d_1} + e_1(1-\varphi)$ $F_{D,\theta=90^\circ} = (a_2 Re^{b_2} + c_2\varphi)(1-\varphi)^{d_2} + e_2(1-\varphi)(Re\varphi + f_2(1-\varphi))$ $F_D = F_{D,\theta=0^\circ} + \frac{1}{2}(F_{D,\theta=90^\circ} - F_{D,\theta=0^\circ})$	$10 \leq Re \leq 300$ $0.1 \leq \varphi \leq 0.3$ $Ar = 0.25$ Oblate cylinders
Cao et.al[42]	$F_D = F_{D0}\varepsilon^{-\alpha\delta-\beta}\omega^{(a_1\theta+a_2)(1-\varepsilon)^{a_3}}, \quad \varepsilon = 1 - \varphi$ $\alpha = 4.988(\varepsilon + 0.5139) - (3.175 - 1.493\varepsilon)\varepsilon^2$ $\delta = \exp[-0.5(1.5 - \log Re)^2] - 0.5884 \log Re$ $\beta = A\varepsilon^3 + B\varepsilon + C$	$10 \leq Re \leq 200$ $0.1 \leq \varphi \leq 0.35$ (sphere and $Ar = 2.5$ ellipsoid) $0.1 \leq \varphi \leq 0.3$ ($Ar = 5$ ellipsoid) $0.1 \leq \varphi \leq 0.2$ ($Ar = 10$ ellipsoid)

192 Against this background, more extensive and detailed simulations are required to bridge current
 193 data gaps and overcome the limitations of existing models in practical applications. Considering the
 194 lack of force correlations for cylindrical biomass particles with $Ar=2.5$ in suspension systems, this
 195 study employs an immersed boundary method particle-resolved direct numerical simulation (IBM-
 196 PR-DNS) framework to systematically explore their hydrodynamic characteristics over $10 \leq Re \leq 2000$
 197 and $0.05 \leq \varphi \leq 0.2$. To validate the simulation framework, the generated data were compared with
 198 previously published results, confirming both accuracy and reliability. Analysis of the surrounding
 199 velocity and vorticity fields revealed how the non-spherical shape of cylindrical particles influences
 200 local flow structures and the resulting hydrodynamic forces. Additionally, the study examined how

201 lift and torque vary with particle orientation, Reynolds number, and volume fraction. Based on these
 202 findings, a novel set of drag, lift, and torque correlations was developed using a genetic algorithm
 203 (GA). These correlations fully incorporate the coupled effects of Re , θ , and φ , and were benchmarked
 204 against existing models for non-spherical particles. The proposed force models, supported by high-
 205 fidelity IBM-PR-DNS data, demonstrate excellent predictive accuracy and general applicability. This
 206 work provides a robust modeling tool for simulating particle dynamics in biomass co-firing systems,
 207 offering novel models for improving combustion performance and promoting efficient biomass
 208 utilization in industrial energy applications.

209 **2. Simulation method and setup**

210 **2.1 Governing equations**

211 This study employed IBM-PR-DNS to investigate the hydrodynamic forces acting on cylindrical
 212 biomass particles with an aspect ratio of $Ar=2.5$ suspension systems in gaseous media with varying
 213 solid volume fractions. The simulations were performed using an in-house CFD solver developed by
 214 Zhang et al. [52, 53], which incorporates a Signed Distance Function Immersed Boundary Method
 215 (SDF-IBM) to enable high-fidelity particle-resolved simulations. The flow was assumed to be
 216 incompressible, with constant physical properties for both phases. Under these assumptions, the
 217 governing equations reduce to the incompressible Navier–Stokes equations, consisting of the
 218 continuity and momentum equations as shown in Eqs. (1)–(2).

219

$$220 \quad \nabla \cdot \overline{\mathbf{u}}_f = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$221 \quad \frac{\partial(\rho_f \overline{\mathbf{u}}_f)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_f \overline{\mathbf{u}}_f \otimes \overline{\mathbf{u}}_f) = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot (\mu_f \nabla \otimes \overline{\mathbf{u}}_f) + \rho_f \overline{\mathbf{g}} + \mathbf{f}_s \quad (2)$$

222 In which, $\overline{\mathbf{u}}_f$ denotes the fluid velocity; ρ_f , p , μ_f , and $\overline{\mathbf{g}}$ represent the fluid density, pressure,

223 kinematic viscosity, and gravitational acceleration, respectively; and t is the time variable. The f_s
 224 refers to the discrete body force applied at the boundary cells to enforce the no-slip boundary
 225 condition.

226 In the SDF-IBM method, the computation of the force term follows the formulation given in Eq.
 227 (3):

$$228 \quad \mathbf{f}_s = \rho_f \varepsilon (\overline{\mathbf{u}}_p - \overline{\mathbf{u}}_f) / \Delta t \quad (3)$$

229 Here, $\overline{\mathbf{u}}_p$ represents the velocity of the solid particle, and ε denotes the solid volume fraction within
 230 each computational cell. For boundary cells, the solid volume fraction is determined using the signed
 231 distance function approach.

232 The governing equations were discretized using a finite volume method based on a non-
 233 staggered grid layout. A second-order central difference scheme was applied for spatial discretization,
 234 with both velocity and pressure defined at the cell centers, and mass fluxes computed at the cell faces.
 235 For time advancement, a projection method was employed, in which an intermediate velocity field is
 236 first predicted, followed by the solution of a pressure Poisson equation to correct the velocity and
 237 enforce the continuity constraint. This method ensures strict satisfaction of the incompressibility
 238 condition throughout the computational domain [44].

239 **2.2 Cylindrical particles definition**

240 The geometry of the straw biomass particles with an average aspect ratio of $Ar=2.5$ was
 241 represented using a superquadric equation. This formulation has been reported in the literature as an
 242 effective and flexible approach for describing both spherical and non-spherical shapes [26, 54]. The
 243 mathematical form is given in Eq. (4).

$$244 \quad (|a \times x|^r + y^r)^{t/r} + |c \times z|^t = 1 \quad (4)$$

245 In this context, x , y , and z denote the three Cartesian coordinate axes. Parameters a and b

246 represent the short semi-axes of the particle base, while c is the semi-length along the axis of the
 247 cylinder. The curvature parameters r and t are set to 1 and 10, respectively, to define the
 248 smoothness of the particle edges. To achieve the desired aspect ratio of $Ar=2.5$, the geometric
 249 parameters are specified as $a=b=3.333$ and $c=1.3333$. The aspect ratio is defined as the ratio of
 250 the semi-length along the axis of rotational symmetry to the base semi-axis, i.e., $Ar = c / a = c / b$.
 251 The angle between the long axis of the cylindrical particles and the direction of the incoming flow is
 252 defined as the incidence angles θ . A local coordinate system is assigned to each particle in the
 253 suspension, as illustrated in Fig. 2. The x' axis is aligned with the local flow direction adjacent to
 254 the particle surface. The y' axis lies in the plane containing the cylindrical symmetry axis s' and
 255 is perpendicular to x' . To form a right-handed coordinate system, the z' axis is always oriented
 256 perpendicular to the $x'y'$ plane.

257
 258 Fig. 2 Geometric model of a straw biomass particle under co-firing (local coordinate system)

259 2.3 Numerical algorithm-immersed boundary method

260 Zhang et al. [52, 53] developed the SDF-IBM framework based on the open-source platform
 261 OpenFOAM. This method solves the velocity and pressure fields using a finite volume projection
 262 algorithm, and couples fluid-particle interactions through a volume-averaged discrete force approach
 263 [55, 56]. The detailed algorithmic steps of the SDF-IBM method are presented in Eqs. (5)-(13).

264 1. Predict the velocity at the next time step (n+1) using the information from the current (n) and
 265 previous (n-1) time steps.

$$266 \quad \frac{\mathbf{u}^* - \mathbf{u}^n}{\Delta t} = -\frac{3}{2}(U^n \cdot \nabla)\mathbf{u}^n + \frac{1}{2}(U^{n-1} \cdot \nabla)\mathbf{u}^{n-1} + \frac{1}{2}v(\nabla^2 \mathbf{u}^* + \nabla^2 \mathbf{u}) \quad (5)$$

267 2. Interpolate the predicted \mathbf{u}^* to the grid face to create the flux field U^* .

268 3. Solve the pressure Poisson equation to obtain the pressure.

$$269 \quad \nabla^2 p = \frac{1}{\Delta t} \nabla \cdot U^* + q_{sf,\Gamma}^{\square} \quad (6)$$

270 4. Use the calculated pressure field to correct the velocity field and flux field.

$$271 \quad \begin{aligned} \tilde{\mathbf{u}} &= \mathbf{u} - \nabla p \cdot \Delta t \\ U^{n-1} &= \mathbf{u}^* - \nabla_f p \cdot \Delta t \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

272 Here, ∇_f is the gradient calculated on the grid face.

273 5. Calculate the fluid-solid coupling force.

$$274 \quad \mathbf{f}_s = \frac{\varepsilon(\mathbf{u}_s^n - \tilde{\mathbf{u}})}{\Delta t} \quad (8)$$

275 Here, ε denotes the solid volume fraction within a computational cell, which is nonzero only when
 276 the solid is either contained in or intersects with the cell. The volume-averaged discrete forcing
 277 method computes the velocity at the boundary cell by averaging the velocities of the fluid and solid
 278 phases weighted by their respective volume fractions.

279 6. Update the fluid velocity to the next time step (n+1) by incorporating the fluid–solid coupling
 280 force.

$$281 \quad \mathbf{u}^{n+1} = \tilde{\mathbf{u}} + \mathbf{f}_s \cdot \Delta t \quad (9)$$

282 7. Calculate the force and torque on the solid from the fluid.

$$283 \quad \mathbf{F}^n = -\rho_f \iiint \mathbf{f} d_v \quad (10)$$

$$284 \quad \mathbf{T}^n = -\rho_f \iiint \mathbf{r} \times \mathbf{f}_s d_v \quad (11)$$

285 Here, r denotes the distance from the center of the grid cell to the center of the solid particle, and
 286 the integration is carried out over the grid cells that contain the solid.

287 8. Update the linear and angular velocities of the solid.

$$288 \quad \mathbf{v}^{n+1} = \mathbf{v}^n + \left(\frac{3}{2}\mathbf{F}^n - \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{F}^{n-1}\right) \cdot \frac{\Delta t}{m} \quad (12)$$

$$289 \quad \boldsymbol{\omega}^{n+1} = \boldsymbol{\omega}^n + \left(\frac{3}{2}\mathbf{T}^n - \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{T}^{n-1}\right) \cdot \frac{\Delta t}{I} \quad (13)$$

290 Here, m is the mass of the particle and I is its moment of inertia. In this study, the particle remains
 291 stationary, and thus this step is omitted.

292 The drag force is defined as the component of the fluid–particle interaction force in the direction
 293 of the local velocity \overline{u}_f , while the lift force corresponds to the component in the local y' direction.
 294 The lateral force is defined as the component in the z' direction. All three force components are
 295 nondimensionalized, as shown in Eq. (14).

$$296 \quad F = \frac{F^n}{3\pi\mu_f D_{eq} u_f} \quad (14)$$

297 In addition to evaluating the translational forces acting on the particle, the torques along the three
 298 directions of the local particle coordinate system are also calculated to investigate the rotational
 299 motion induced by different flow conditions. In this context, the normalized torque T_f is defined
 300 analogously to the force normalization, as shown in Eq. (15).

$$301 \quad T_f = \frac{T^n}{3\pi\mu_f D_{eq} u_f \cdot \frac{D_{eq}}{2}} \quad (15)$$

302 The aerodynamic coefficients of a single particle can be calculated using Eq. (16) [30, 31].

$$303 \quad C_D = \frac{|F_D|}{\frac{1}{2}\rho_f A^* |\overline{u}_f - \overline{u}_p|^2}, C_L = \frac{|F_L|}{\frac{1}{2}\rho_f A^* |\overline{u}_f - \overline{u}_p|^2}, C_T = \frac{|T_f|}{\frac{1}{2}\rho_f A^* |\overline{u}_f - \overline{u}_p|^2 \cdot \frac{D_{eq}}{2}} \quad (16)$$

304 In this expression, F_D , F_L , and T_f represent the drag, lift, and torque exerted by the fluid on the
 305 particle, respectively, while $A^* = \pi D_{eq}^2 / 4$ denotes the projected cross-sectional area of the cylindrical
 306 particle based on its equivalent spherical volume.

307 The Reynolds number is defined based on the characteristic length of the particle (d) and the
 308 average fluid velocity ($\overline{u_f}$) within the computational domain, as shown in Eq. (17):

$$309 \quad Re = \frac{\rho_f \overline{u_f} d}{\mu_f} \quad (17)$$

310 For non-spherical cylindrical particles, the Reynolds number is defined as shown in Eq. (18):

$$311 \quad Re = \frac{\rho_f |\overline{u_f} - \overline{u_p}| D_{eq}}{\mu_f} \quad (18)$$

312 Where, D_{eq} denotes the equivalent spherical diameter corresponding to the volume V_p of the non-
 313 spherical particle, and the characteristic length is defined as $D_{eq} = (6V_p / \pi)^{1/3}$. The term $|\overline{u_f} - \overline{u_p}|$
 314 represents the relative velocity between the fluid and the particle.

315 Regarding the mesh model, we used a uniform Cartesian background mesh for coupling with
 316 the immersed boundary method. The grid consists of uniform cubic cells, with a resolution of 50 grid
 317 points per particle equivalent diameter (i.e., grid spacing $\Delta = D_{ep}/50$). For a typical domain of size
 318 $35D_{ep} \times 12D_{ep} \times 12D_{ep}$, the total number of grid points is approximately 10 million.

319 **2.4 Computational domain and particle suspension generation**

320 In this study, a rectangular computational domain with dimensions $35D_{eq} \times 12D_{eq} \times 12D_{eq}$
 321 (length \times width \times height) was established, as illustrated in Fig. 3. A uniform and constant inlet velocity
 322 was applied in the x -direction, while the outlet was treated with a fixed-pressure condition and a zero-
 323 gradient velocity outflow to ensure the formation of a stable streamwise flow. Periodic boundary
 324 conditions were applied in the lateral y and z directions to mimic the unbounded characteristics of the
 325 suspension system. To minimize the influence of wall and inlet/outlet effects on the particle group,

326 particles were distributed only within a central subregion of $15 \times 10 \times 10$, which spans approximately
 327 half the domain length. The total number of particles was determined based on the prescribed solid
 328 volume fraction ϕ , as given by Eq. (19).

$$329 \quad N = \frac{6\phi V}{\pi D_{eq}^3} \quad (19)$$

330 Here, V denotes the volume of the computational domain containing the particles, and N is the
 331 total number of particles within the domain. The solid volume fractions examined are 0.05, 0.10, 0.15,
 332 and 0.20, corresponding to particle counts of 176, 353, 530, and 707, respectively.

333
 334 Fig. 3 3D view of the cylindrical Multi-particle suspension in the computational domain

335 To accurately define the initial state of the particle suspension system, a custom particle
 336 generation procedure was implemented in Unity using tailored scripts and the built-in generation
 337 functions. A Cartesian coordinate system was established within a cuboid domain identical in size to
 338 the computational setup. Cylindrical particles with a fixed $Ar=2.5$ were randomly initialized with
 339 various positions and orientations. Under gravity or applied forces, the particles were allowed to move
 340 freely, collide, and settle. Throughout the simulation, a real-time collision detection algorithm

341 ensured that no overlap occurred between particles, as illustrated in Fig. 4(a). Once all particles
 342 reached a mechanically stable and non-overlapping state, the simulation was paused, and the full
 343 dataset of particle coordinates and orientations was exported. The generated particle location and
 344 orientation data are imported into the initial input data of the IBM-PR-DNS simulation in the
 345 subsequent SDF-IBM code environment, developed based on the open-source software OpenFOAM.
 346 This ensures that the initial particle distribution state of the numerical simulation is fully consistent
 347 with the spatial layout generated by Unity, as illustrated in Fig. 4(b).

348

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Fig. 4 Suspended particle system with $\phi=0.05$ and $Ar=2.5$:

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(a) Particle initialization generated in Unity; (b) Initial configuration imported into IBM-PR-DNS.

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A total of over 200 simulations were conducted, spanning various Re , ϕ , and θ . For $Re \leq 100$, the flow remained stable; when Re exceeded 100, unsteady flow behavior emerged. Each simulation was run until the time averaged drag, lift, lateral force, and torque converged to steady values. To avoid boundary-induced bias near the inlet and outlet, only particles located between $x=6D_{eq}$ and $x=19D_{eq}$ were selected for force analysis. The hydrodynamic forces on these particles were post-processed using MATLAB, and averaged for each incidence angles interval of $\Delta\theta = 10^\circ$. Starting from $\theta=5^\circ$, nine particle orientation intervals were analyzed in total, as summarized in Table 2.

Table 2 Parameter ranges used in the numerical simulations

Parameter	Setting range
Re	10,100,300,500,1000,2000
θ	5°, 15°, 25°, 35°, 45°, 55°, 65°, 75°, 85°
φ	0.05, 0.1, 0.15, 0.2
$\Phi(N)$	0.05(176), 0.1(353), 0.15(530), 0.2(707)

359 To further validate the randomness of particle orientations within the suspension system, a
360 statistical analysis of the incidence angles was conducted. Here, it satisfies the relation $\theta = 90^\circ - \gamma$,
361 where the unit vector γ is the angle along the axis of rotational symmetry with the x' axis.
362 According to the theory of random orientation in three-dimensional space, the distribution of θ should
363 follow either a $\cos(\theta)$ pattern. As illustrated in Fig. 5, the normalized particle count in each
364 $\Delta\theta = 10^\circ$ interval closely matches the expected $\cos(\theta)$ distribution. This confirms that, under all
365 examined solid volume fractions, the particles are randomly oriented, thereby providing a statistically
366 valid initial condition for subsequent force and motion analyses.

367 An orientation tensor was used to quantitatively evaluate the spatial alignment of cylindrical
368 particles in the suspension system [44]. For a truly random distribution, the diagonal components of
369 the tensor along the x , y , and z axes should each be one-third, while the off-diagonal terms should
370 approach zero. This reflects the absence of any preferential particle orientation. Results show that for
371 solid volume fractions of 0.05, 0.1, 0.15, and 0.2, the maximum deviation of the diagonal tensor
372 components remains within 0.333 ± 0.005 . This confirms that particles exhibit a high degree of random
373 orientation across all tested solid volume fractions.

Fig. 5 Orientation distribution of cylindrical particles under different ϕ

2.5 Background mesh, model validation and domain independence study

To ensure the accuracy of hydrodynamic calculations for non-spherical particle suspensions, a uniform Cartesian background mesh was employed for spatial discretization. In this study, the IBM-PR-DNS method is employed to resolve the particle–fluid interface without requiring mesh deformation or local refinement. However, the overall mesh resolution must be sufficiently fine to accurately capture flow structures around the particle surfaces[26, 42, 44]. Based on prior simulation experience and best practices reported in the literature, approximately 50 grid cells were allocated across the particle's characteristic dimension, corresponding to a grid spacing of roughly 1/50 of the equivalent-volume diameter D_{eq} . The computational domain used in this study also exceeds the typical domain sizes reported in existing studies. To confirm the adequacy of this resolution, a grid independence test was conducted for a representative isolated particle case involving a cylindrical particle with $Ar=2.5$, $Re=2000$, and $\theta=45^\circ$. The drag coefficient C_D , lift coefficient C_L , and torque

388 coefficient C_T were computed under coarse ($\Delta=D_{eq}/40$ cells), baseline ($\Delta=D_{eq}/50$ cells), and refined
389 ($\Delta=D_{eq}/60$ cells) mesh configurations. As shown in Table 3, refining the grid from $\Delta=D_{eq}/40$ to 50
390 cells resulted in changes of less than 2% for all force components, indicating that grid independence
391 was achieved. Therefore, all subsequent simulations in this study adopted a resolution of $\Delta=D_{eq}/50$
392 cells, balancing computational accuracy with efficiency.

393 Table 3 Comparison of results for $Ar=2.5$ isolated cylindrical particles at different grid
394 resolutions. ($\theta=45^\circ$, $Re=2000$)

$Re=2000$		Coarse mesh		Medium mesh		Fine mesh
C_D		0.8642		0.8625		0.8623
C_L	$\Delta=D_{eq}/40$	0.4537	$\Delta=D_{eq}/50$	0.4505	$\Delta=D_{eq}/60$	0.4502
C_T		0.9634		0.9602		0.9601

395
396 In addition to the grid independence verification, a comparative analysis with existing literature
397 was conducted to further validate the computational domain setup, mesh resolution, and numerical
398 methodology employed in this study. Specifically, a benchmark case involving particles with $Ar=0.25$
399 at $\varphi=0.2$ and $Re=300$ was selected. The F_D , F_L , and F_T obtained from the present IBM-PR-DNS
400 simulations were systematically compared with the results reported by Cao and Tafti [44] to assess
401 the applicability of the current approach in dense non-spherical particle suspensions. In the
402 comparison, the particle forces were averaged within incidence angles intervals of $\Delta\theta=10^\circ$. As
403 shown in Table 4, the computed values closely match the reference data across the entire angular
404 range. The maximum relative deviation in drag was 1.7% at $\theta=65^\circ$, the highest discrepancy in lift
405 was 2.57% at $\theta=35^\circ$, and the largest torque deviation was 2.98% at $\theta=55^\circ$. These results demonstrate
406 that the present IBM-PR-DNS framework maintains high predictive accuracy not only for isolated
407 particles but also for densely packed suspensions. The findings reinforce the robustness and reliability

408 of the proposed method in simulating force characteristics of non-spherical particles in multiparticle
 409 systems.

410 Table 4 Comparison of simulation results for $Ar=0.25$ cylindrical particle suspensions

411 ($\varphi=0.2, Re=300$) R denotes relative error $|F_{Cao\&Tafti} - F_{Present}| / F_{Cao\&Tafti} \times 100\%$

θ ($^\circ$)	F_D			F_L			F_T		
	Cao and Tafti	Present	R^*	Cao and Tafti	Present	R^{**}	Cao and Tafti	Present	R^{***}
	[26]	IBM	(%)	[26]	IBM	(%)	[26]	IBM	(%)
5	32.874	33.420	1.661	0.396	0.389	1.768	3.560	3.516	1.235
15	41.075	41.523	1.091	1.386	1.359	1.948	12.355	12.145	1.699
25	47.303	47.825	1.103	1.584	1.604	1.262	16.898	16.645	1.497
35	62.579	63.487	1.451	2.178	2.234	2.571	21.989	21.356	2.878
45	74.746	75.774	1.375	2.376	2.418	1.767	22.559	21.935	2.766
55	77.574	78.504	1.198	1.980	1.942	1.919	17.795	17.265	2.978
65	84.363	85.761	1.657	1.287	1.265	1.709	14.073	13.912	1.144
75	84.931	83.585	1.584	1.089	1.075	1.2855	12.654	13.002	2.751
85	94.552	95.973	1.502	0.396	0.401	1.263	2.532	2.598	2.607

412 We conducted a detailed domain independence test as illustrated in the Table 5. Four domain
 413 sizes were examined: streamwise lengths x -axis of $32D_{ep}$, $35D_{ep}$, $38D_{ep}$, and $41D_{ep}$, with cross-stream
 414 widths y -axis and heights z -axis of $10D_{ep}$, $12D_{ep}$, $14D_{ep}$, and $16D_{ep}$, respectively. The analysis was
 415 performed under a representative condition with particle incidence angles $\theta=45^\circ$, Reynolds number
 416 $Re=2000$, and solid volume fraction $\varphi=0.2$. Drag force (F_D), lift force (F_L), and torque (F_T) acting on
 417 the particles were computed for each domain size, using the results from the largest domain
 418 ($41D_{ep} \times 16D_{ep} \times 16D_{ep}$) as the reference to evaluate relative errors. When the computational domain
 419 size reaches $35D_{ep} \times 12D_{ep} \times 12D_{ep}$, the relative errors in drag, lift, and torque compared with the largest
 420 domain reduce significantly to 0.625%, 0.784%, and 1.691%, respectively. Increasing the domain
 421 further to $38D_{ep} \times 14D_{ep} \times 14D_{ep}$ results in minimal further reduction of errors (0.282%, 0.401%, and
 422 1.044%, respectively), indicating negligible improvement (less than 1% difference). Therefore,
 423 considering both computational accuracy and efficiency, we chose $35D_{ep} \times 12D_{ep} \times 12D_{ep}$ as the

424 optimal domain size for this study.

425 Table 5 Domain independency study of the averaged forces for $Ar=2.5$ with the particle
 426 orientation of $\theta = 45^\circ$ at $Re = 2000$.

427 E denotes relative error $\left| \frac{F_{IBM} - F_{41D_{eq} \times 16D_{eq} \times 16D_{eq}}}{F_{41D_{eq} \times 16D_{eq} \times 16D_{eq}}} \times 100\% \right|$

Domain size ($x \times y \times z$)	$F_D (\theta = 45^\circ, \varphi = 0.2, Re = 2000)$		$F_L (\theta = 45^\circ, \varphi = 0.2, Re = 2000)$		$F_T (\theta = 45^\circ, \varphi = 0.2, Re = 2000)$	
	Present	E^*	Present	E^{**}	Present	E^{***}
	IBM	(%)	IBM	(%)	IBM	(%)
$32D_{ep} \times 10D_{ep} \times 10D_{ep}$	335.480	11.391	86.708	6.434	90.192	4.918
$35D_{ep} \times 12D_{ep} \times 12D_{ep}$	303.057	0.625	82.105	0.784	87.418	1.691
$38D_{ep} \times 14D_{ep} \times 14D_{ep}$	302.025	0.282	81.792	0.401	86.862	1.044
$41D_{ep} \times 16D_{ep} \times 16D_{ep}$	301.173	-	81.466	-	85.964	-

428

429 3. Results and discussion

430 3.1 Flow field and structural characteristics of cylindrical particle suspensions

431 To investigate the influence of Reynolds number, incidence angle, and solid volume fraction on
 432 the hydrodynamic forces of cylindrical particle suspensions, key flow and structural features are
 433 visualized under selected representative conditions. The analysis first focuses on the effect of
 434 Reynolds number, followed by an examination of inter-particle disturbances due to varying solid
 435 volume fractions.

436 Figure 6 presents the non-dimensional interstitial u^* velocity in the x -direction for cylindrical
 437 particles with $Ar=2.5$ at $\varphi=0.1$, under four different Reynolds numbers ($Re=10, 300, 1000, \text{ and } 2000$).
 438 The evolution of the velocity field around the non-spherical particles demonstrates the transition from
 439 viscous dominated to inertia driven flow regimes as Re increases. At $Re=10$, the flow remains smooth
 440 and stable, with large scale, gradual velocity transitions indicating viscous dominated behavior. Short,
 441 symmetric wakes appear behind the particles, and blue isosurfaces indicate local low velocity regions
 442 near the rear, while the mainstream velocity remains high. As Re increases to 300, the flow enters a

443 transitional regime characterized by periodic vortex shedding. Alternating high and low speed regions
444 form in the particle wakes, and the wake becomes longer and wider. The velocity field shows more
445 complex spatial variation, with low-speed streaks surrounded by faster fluid zones. At higher
446 Reynolds numbers ($Re=1000$ and 2000), inertia dominates the flow dynamics. The wake becomes
447 increasingly populated with vortices of varying scales, and the velocity field shows a fragmented
448 pattern with alternating high speed (red) and low speed (blue) regions. At $Re=2000$, the flow exhibits
449 typical turbulent characteristics, including strong velocity fluctuations, intense wake shear, and
450 widespread turbulent energy distribution. Previous studies have shown that vortex shedding and
451 turbulent pulsations in high Re flows are key contributors to increased drag and energy dissipation
452 [57]. These findings are consistent with classical wake transition behavior around isolated particles
453 [58] and also highlight the complex flow patterns arising from the wake interactions in particle
454 ensembles [59]. In particle laden suspensions, neighboring particles disrupt and block each other's
455 wakes, reducing flow sensitivity to inertia and altering force distributions based on inter particle
456 distance and Reynolds number [60]. Notably, for $\phi>0.05$, local interactions between nearby particles
457 significantly disturb individual wakes, which explains the pronounced impact of inertial effects on
458 the macroscopic flow behavior of such suspensions [61].

459 The vorticity field of cylindrical particles with $Ar=2.5$ and $\phi=0.1$ was visualized using the Q-
460 criterion proposed by Hunt et al. [62] under $Re=100$, 1000 , and 2000 . The results clearly demonstrate
461 the influence of inertial forces on the structure of the flow field across different Re conditions. At
462 $Re=100$, the flow remains primarily viscous dominated, exhibiting symmetric and stable
463 characteristics with weak vortex structures. As Re increases to 1000 and 2000 , inertia becomes
464 dominant, leading to the formation of vortex shedding and asymmetric, three dimensional wake
465 instabilities. These observations are consistent with the classical wake transition behavior observed

466 in isolated particles flows [26, 30, 31, 63]. However, in the context of multi-particle suspensions,
 467 local vorticity structures are found to be prematurely disturbed due to interactions with neighboring
 468 particles, highlighting the significant role of collective effects in modifying the flow dynamics.

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Fig. 6. Flow field of different Re cylindrical particles suspension at $Ar=2.5$, $\phi = 0.1$.

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Fig. 7. Visualization of the Q-criterion vorticity of different Re cylindrical particles suspension
 at $Ar=2.5$, $\phi = 0.1$.

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In addition to Re , the ϕ plays a crucial role in determining the flow structure within particle
 suspensions. Figure 8 illustrates the typical distributions of non-dimensional interstitial velocity (u^*
 in the x direction) around cylindrical particles at a fixed $Re=500$ for various volume fractions ($\phi=$
 0.05, 0.10, 0.15, and 0.20). As ϕ increases, significant changes are observed in both the flow pathways

478 and velocity distribution within the suspension. At the lowest concentration ($\phi=0.05$), particles are
479 sparsely distributed, allowing the fluid to pass relatively uniformly through the voids. The velocity
480 field resembles a superposition of flows around isolated particles, with low overall resistance. When
481 ϕ increases to 0.10, the average particle spacing decreases, and the flow becomes more constrained.
482 Narrow flow channels with slightly elevated velocities begin to emerge, forming preliminary
483 "preferential paths," indicating that some downstream particles are influenced by the wake of
484 upstream ones, resulting in localized flow interference. At $\phi=0.15$ the flow inhomogeneity becomes
485 more pronounced, the fluid is forced through the limited pore space, creating a noticeable high speed
486 flow in some interconnected channels, while blocked regions show large low speed zones. This
487 indicates a coexistence of preferential and stagnant flow regions, with the fluid preferentially passing
488 through lower resistance paths. When ϕ reaches 0.20, such inhomogeneity reaches its maximum. The
489 suspension exhibits well defined high-speed main channels guiding most of the flow across the
490 domain, while many regions behind particles or in narrow gaps fall into recirculation or dead zones.
491 At the macroscopic level, increasing ϕ leads to reduced permeability and higher flow resistance; at
492 the microscopic level, the flow transitions from uniform to highly inhomogeneity, with large velocity
493 gradients. These findings are consistent with experimental observations by Vollmari et al. [64] in
494 irregular particle beds, where variations in particle orientation under different volume fractions
495 enhance flow inhomogeneity, forming alternating "fast channels" and "slow zones," directly affecting
496 the distribution of hydrodynamic forces on the particles.

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Fig. 8. Flow field of different ϕ cylindrical particles suspension at $Ar=2.5$, $Re = 500$.

499 3.2 Drag of suspension systems

500 In particle laden suspension systems, even under identical macroscopic conditions—such as Re
 501 and ϕ —the instantaneous drag experienced by individual particles can vary significantly due to local
 502 flow fluctuations and differences in particle orientation. Figure 9 illustrates the relationship between
 503 the average force on the number of particles in the $\Delta\theta = 10^\circ$ between the resistance and the
 504 incidence angles of the particles at $Re=10$ and $Re=2000$ for solid fractions of $\phi=0.05$ and 0.2
 505 respectively. (Each blue dot in the figure represents a particle in the suspension system and the pink
 506 dots represent the average value of the particles in the $\Delta\theta \pm 5^\circ$ range). A total of 155 data points
 507 were recorded for $\phi= 0.05$ and 682 data points for $\phi= 0.20$.

508 Under low $Re=10$ conditions with $\phi= 0.05$ and 0.20 , the total drag on the cylindrical particles
 509 shows minimal variation with increasing θ . This behavior is primarily attributed to the dominance of
 510 viscous forces at low Re . As the particle orientation shifts toward higher incident angles, the projected
 511 area in the streamwise direction decreases, thereby reducing the contribution of viscous drag. But the

512 overall difference is small. For instance, at $\varphi=0.05$, the drag force decreases from 3.23 at $\theta=5^\circ$ to
513 2.467 at $\theta=85^\circ$, a reduction of only 0.763. Similarly, at $\varphi=0.20$, the drag drops from 10.631 to 9.195
514 over the same angular range, yielding a difference of just 1.436. These results indicate that under
515 viscous dominated conditions, particle orientation has a relatively weak influence on total drag.

516 At a high $Re=2000$ and $\varphi=0.05$ and 0.20, the total drag force exerted on cylindrical particles is
517 predominantly governed by pressure drag. As the θ decreases, the pressure contribution to the total
518 drag increases significantly, indicating that the overall drag becomes more sensitive to variations in
519 the pressure field. While the angular trend of drag is similar to that observed for isolated cylindrical
520 particles [31], the magnitude of drag variation at a given angle is much larger in a suspended particle
521 system. This finding is consistent with the observations by He and Tafti [41], who reported similar
522 behavior for ellipsoidal particles with a sphericity of 0.887 at $\varphi=0.35$. The orientation of non-spherical
523 particles has a strong influence on their drag. For the elongated cylindrical particles considered in this
524 study ($Ar=2.5$), variations in the θ lead to significant changes in the projected frontal area and flow
525 separation characteristics, resulting in marked differences in drag. Generally, when the particle's long
526 axis is aligned with the flow direction (small θ), the projected area is minimized and drag is lowest.
527 Conversely, when the long axis is perpendicular to the flow (large θ), the projected area and drag
528 reach their maximum values [5, 26]. Under $Re=2000$ and $\varphi=0.20$, the drag at $\theta=85^\circ$ is only 53.67%
529 of the value at $\theta=5^\circ$, highlighting the strong orientation effect. This drag trend agrees well with the
530 results of Sanjeevi and Padding [65], who used the LBM to simulate elongated ellipsoids with $Ar =$
531 2.5.

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Fig. 9. Variation of F_D with θ for cylindrical particles at Re and φ

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To better illustrate the variation of drag force with particle orientation and flow conditions, the drag values were normalized using the force at $F_{D,\Delta\theta=0-10^\circ}$. As shown in Fig. 10(a), the relative drag force exhibits a clear decreasing trend as the θ increases from 0° to 90° . This trend is attributed to the reduction in projected frontal area, which decreases the effective drag force acting along the flow direction. Under high $Re=2000$ conditions, the decrease is more pronounced, reaching 46.33%, indicating that particle orientation has a stronger influence on hydrodynamic forces in inertial dominated flows. In contrast, at a higher $\varphi=0.2$, the drag reduction is significant compared to $\varphi=0.05$, where the drop reaches 59.22%. This discrepancy is likely due to the spatial redistribution of neighboring particles in dense systems, where shielding and wake interference improved the sensitivity of local flow structures to orientation changes. Furthermore, the averaged drag force under

545 different Re conditions is presented in Fig. 10(b). The results reveal that the average drag force
 546 increases consistently with both Re and φ . For all φ values, drag grows nearly linearly with Re ,
 547 indicating that increased flow inertia enhances the momentum exchange between particles and the
 548 surrounding fluid. At a fixed Re , a higher φ results in stronger particle-particle interactions, including
 549 shielding effects, wake overlap, and local velocity distortions, all of which contribute to intensified
 550 force inhomogeneity and higher overall drag. Overall, the drag force increases steadily in the low Re
 551 range ($Re < 1000$), while for $Re > 1000$, the rate of increase becomes significantly steeper with
 552 increasing φ .

553
 554 Fig. 10. Variation of F_D on cylindrical particles under different Re and φ :
 555 (a) Dependence of F_D on incident angle θ ; (b) Evolution of total F_D with Re .

556 Based on the above trends, the incidence angles has a pronounced effect on the drag force
 557 experienced by non-spherical particles. While existing models for isolated particles often incorporate
 558 the influence of the incidence angles, many drag correlations for particle laden suspensions still rely
 559 on empirical correction factors that depend solely on the Reynolds number and solid volume fraction,
 560 without accounting for particle orientation. However, simulation results indicate that such traditional
 561 approaches are insufficient to accurately capture the orientation induced drag variations in cylindrical
 562 particles within suspensions. Therefore, a more correlation models is needed—one that

563 simultaneously accounts for Re , φ , and θ .

564 Under low Re conditions (Stokes flow), Happel and Brenner [66] were among the first to propose
565 that the drag coefficient of an isolated non-spherical particle can be described as a function of θ , as
566 given by Eq. (20).

$$567 \quad C_{D,\theta} = C_{D,\theta=0^\circ} + (C_{D,\theta=90^\circ} - C_{D,\theta=0^\circ})\sin^2(\theta) \quad (20)$$

568 The drag coefficient of a single non-spherical particle is commonly described using angle
569 dependent expressions based on the Happel-Brenner formulation. This approach has been
570 successfully applied by Ouchene et al. [28], Sanjeevi et al. [65, 67], and Chen et al. [54] to capture
571 the drag behavior of prolate and oblate ellipsoids. Similarly, Cao and Tafti [26] demonstrated that the
572 formula yields prediction errors of less than 10% for disk-shaped particles with $Ar=0.25$ at Re below
573 50. Moreover, Sanjeevi and Padding [68] extended its applicability to elongated spherocylinders with
574 $Ar=4$ even under dense suspension conditions ($\varphi=0.5$). However, among these efforts, only the work
575 of Cao and Tafti [44] explicitly incorporated the influence of particle incidence angles into drag
576 correlations for non-spherical particles in suspensions.

577 Motivated by these findings, a novel drag correlation has been developed in this study for
578 cylindrical particles with $Ar=2.5$, valid across a solid volume fraction range of $0.05 \leq \varphi \leq 0.2$.
579 Preliminary analysis indicates that the drag exhibits a sinusoidal dependence ($\sin\theta$) on the incidence
580 angles, effectively capturing the force variation observed in suspensions. The proposed correlation is
581 presented in Eqs. (21)–(23). When a cylindrical particle is inclined at an angle θ to the freestream
582 direction, both the projected frontal area and wake asymmetry vary with θ . The asymmetry in the
583 flow separation becomes most pronounced around $\theta \approx 45^\circ$, leading to a maximum imbalance in
584 pressure distribution on the particle's upper and lower surfaces. This imbalance generates peak lift
585 and torque responses, as confirmed by our IBM-PR-DNS results. The $\sin\theta$ function naturally captures

586 this trend—vanishing at $\theta=0^\circ$ and $\theta=90^\circ$, and peaking at $\theta=45^\circ$, which aligns well with our simulation
 587 data.

$$588 \quad F_{D,\theta} = F_{D,\theta=0^\circ} + (F_{D,\theta=90^\circ} - F_{D,\theta=0^\circ}) \sin^{G_1}(\theta) \quad (21)$$

$$589 \quad F_{D,\theta=0^\circ} = (a_1 Re^{a_2} + a_3(1-\varphi))(1-\varphi)^{a_4} + a_5(1-\varphi)(Re \cdot \varphi + a_6(1-\varphi)) \quad (22)$$

$$590 \quad F_{D,\theta=90^\circ} = (b_1 Re^{b_2} + b_3\varphi)(1-\varphi)^{b_4} + b_5(1-\varphi)(Re \cdot \varphi + b_6(1-\varphi)) \quad (23)$$

591 Here, $F_{D,\theta=0^\circ}$ and $F_{D,\theta=90^\circ}$ represent the drag forces experienced by a particle at incidence angles
 592 of 0° and 90° , respectively. This formulation mirrors the sinusoidal relations commonly found in the
 593 literature, capturing the dependence of drag on particle orientation. One of the key advantages of this
 594 approach is that it requires only two representative drag values to characterize the full angular
 595 behavior. However, in particle laden suspensions, precisely aligned particles at $\theta=0^\circ$ or $\theta=90^\circ$ are
 596 rarely observed. To overcome this challenge, we approximate these values by averaging the forces
 597 exerted on particles with incidence angles in the ranges of $0^\circ < \theta < 10^\circ$ and $80^\circ < \theta < 90^\circ$, respectively,
 598 yielding estimates at $\theta=5^\circ$ and $\theta=85^\circ$.

599 To optimize the fitting parameters of the proposed correlation, a genetic algorithm (GA) [69-72]
 600 was employed. The parameter sets obtained from a least squares regression were used as the initial
 601 population, with a population size of 6800, a maximum of 500 iterations, a migration rate of 0.5, and
 602 a crossover rate of 0.6. Both linear and nonlinear constraints were imposed to ensure the physical
 603 feasibility of the solution. The optimization objective was to minimize the root mean square error
 604 (RMSE) between the simulation results and model predictions. The final optimized coefficients are
 605 summarized in Table 6. For particle suspensions, the mean drag force can be computed using Eq.
 606 (21)–(23), by averaging the total force exerted on all particles and dividing it by the number of
 607 particles at a given solid volume fraction.

608 Table 6 Correlation fitting optimized coefficients used in F_D

i	1	2	3	4	5	6
$F_{D,\theta=0^\circ} a_i$	0.0217	1.0524	2.7516	-4.5248	0.5245	1.3689
$F_{D,\theta=90^\circ} b_i$	0.0105	0.9464	3.6307	-8.1466	0.2995	13.5469
G_i	3.4657			-		

609 The three expressions collectively establish a novel drag correlation model tailored for particle
610 suspensions, which explicitly incorporates a sinusoidal dependence on the θ while accounting for the
611 effects of both φ and Re , including their coupling. As illustrated in Fig. 11, the correlation model
612 demonstrates that the use of a $\sin\theta$ effectively captures the variation in drag with particle orientation.
613 Across the entire tested range of Re and φ , the model predictions show excellent agreement with the
614 original IBM-PR-DNS data. The root mean square error (RMSE) of the novel model is 0.463, with a
615 coefficient of determination (R^2) reaching 0.9999. The mean relative error is 4.39%, and the median
616 relative error is 5.08%. Although the drag data span a broad range (from 0 to 360), which may lead
617 to differing sensitivity at the upper and lower ends of the value range, the overall fitting accuracy
618 remains within acceptable limits. These statistical metrics confirm that the proposed model reliably
619 captures the drag characteristics of cylindrical particle under varying flow conditions, offering high
620 predictive accuracy and strong generalizability.

621 Fig. 11. Comparison between IBM-PR-DNS drag data and the correlation of the novel model.

622 Symbol: IBM-PR-DNS data; Dashed line: correlation prediction

623 3.2 Lift of suspension systems

624 The lift force experienced by non-spherical particles in a flow primarily originates from their
 625 geometric asymmetry and the presence of a nonzero incidence angles. When fluid flows around a
 626 tilted cylindrical particle, an imbalance in pressure distribution between the front and rear surfaces
 627 generates a net lift force in the plane perpendicular to the main flow direction. To investigate this
 628 effect in suspensions of $Ar=2.5$ cylindrical particles, the lift and lateral forces on each particles were
 629 computed in their local coordinate systems, using absolute values. The Fig. 12 presents the variation
 630 of lift and lateral forces with particle orientation.
 631

632 The lift force exhibits a distinct trend from drag. It approaches zero at symmetric orientations
 633 ($\theta=0^\circ$ and 90°), and reaches a peak in the intermediate range of $35^\circ < \theta < 55^\circ$, with a maximum at $\theta=45^\circ$.

634 This is consistent with the findings of Andersson and Jiang [73], who reported that for elongated
635 ellipsoids with $Ar=6$, the lift coefficient at $\theta=45^\circ$ reaches about 20% of the drag coefficient, while it
636 tends to zero at $\theta=0^\circ$ or 90° . As illustrated in Fig. 12(a), under low Re conditions, lift fluctuations
637 remain modest, with values ranging from 0.2 to 0.4. This suggests that viscous dominated flows exert
638 weak transverse forces on non-spherical particles, and the influence of orientation is limited. In
639 contrast, Fig. 12(c) reveals a sharp increase in lift with θ at high Re , peaking around $\theta=45^\circ$ and
640 decreasing thereafter. This behavior aligns with classical lift mechanisms, where asymmetric wake
641 structures caused by inclined inflow enhance transverse pressure gradients. Similar observations were
642 reported by Ouchene et al. [74] for ellipsoidal particles. Moreover, at high $\varphi=0.2$, the intensified
643 particle particle hydrodynamic interactions lead to more pronounced variability in lift forces. This
644 indicates that local arrangements and shielding effects contribute to greater flow instability and lift
645 fluctuations. As illustrated in Fig. 12(b) and (d), each particles exhibit strong positive and negative
646 variations in both lift and lateral forces. While the average lift shows clear dependence on θ , the
647 average lateral force remains nearly zero overall. However, under $Re=2000$ and $\varphi=0.2$, lateral force
648 fluctuations become more prominent, suggesting that non-spherical particles are highly sensitive to
649 unsteady flow disturbances.

650

651

Fig. 12. Variation of F_L and $F_{Lateral}$ with θ for cylindrical particles at Re and ϕ

652

653

For isolated particle lift coefficients, Happel and Brenner [66] also proposed a set of linear theoretical expressions under Stokes flow conditions, as given in Eq. (24).

654

$$C_{L,\theta} = (C_{D,\theta=90^\circ} - C_{D,\theta=0^\circ}) \sin(\theta) \cos(\theta) \quad (24)$$

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661

Although the expression has been effectively used by Cao and Tafti [26], Mema et al. [75], and Lote et al. [41] to describe lift forces on isolated ellipsoidal and disk-shaped particles, it has not yet been thoroughly validated for multiparticle suspension systems. Due to the lack of reliable lift force correlations for cylindrical particles in the literature, we developed a novel lift force model tailored for suspension systems using GA. The corresponding correlation is given in Eq. (25) and (26), and the optimized fitting parameters are listed in Table 7.

$$F_{L,\theta} = (F_{D,\theta=90^\circ} - F_{D,\theta=0^\circ}) \sin(\theta) \cos(\theta) \quad (25)$$

662
$$F_{L,\theta} = c_1 \sin(\theta) \cos(\theta) (c_2 - \varphi)^3 / (1 + c_3 / \varphi - (c_4 / Re - (1 / (c_4 - \varphi)^2))) \quad (26)$$

663 Table 7 Correlation fitting optimized coefficients used in F_L

i	1	2	3	4	5
c_i	3473.8577	-0.5229	-0.0795	17398.1278	-74.968

664 In suspension systems, the average lift force can be determined using Eq. (26), following the
665 same approach as for drag force calculation. The Fig. 13 presents a comparison between the
666 predictions of the novel lift model and the IBM-PR-DNS simulation results, indicating that the model
667 effectively captures the lift force across varying Re , φ , and θ . Unlike the asymmetric lift distribution
668 observed for isolated cylindrical particles [31], the lift distribution in the suspension system is more
669 symmetric. An increase in the φ enhances the flow interactions and wake interference among particles,
670 which significantly contributes to the observed rise in lift. A greater number of particles intensifies
671 velocity gradients in the flow field—accelerated and decelerated zones—resulting in stronger shear
672 forces that elevate peak lift values. At a constant φ , increasing Re also substantially amplifies lift. For
673 instance, at $\varphi=0.2$, the peak lift at $Re=2000$ exceeds 80, while it is only around 10 at $Re=300$,
674 underscoring the strong influence of fluid inertia on asymmetric wake formation and lift generation.
675 The novel developed lift model successfully captures the nonlinear lift variation with flow conditions
676 and particle orientation. The model's predictions show excellent agreement with the IBM-PR-DNS
677 data, reflecting its strong physical consistency and generalizability. The model achieves a root-mean-
678 square error (RMSE) of 0.131, a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.9995, an average relative error
679 of 4.98%, and a median relative error of 6.41%.

680
681 Fig. 13. Comparison between IBM-PR-DNS lift data and the correlation of the novel model.

682 Symbol: IBM-PR-DNS data; Dashed line: correlation prediction

683 3.3 Torque of suspension systems

684 The fluid induced torque on particles plays a critical role in determining their orientation stability.

685 In industrial simulations of multi-particle suspension systems, angular momentum transfer is typically
686 modeled through particle-particle collision dynamics. While this approach is effective for spherical
687 particles, it becomes cannot be ignored for non-spherical particles, where the fluid torque must be
688 explicitly considered. To obtain accurate numerical data, the normalized fluid torque was computed
689 along the three principal axes of the local particle coordinate system, and the absolute values were
690 analyzed, as illustrated in Fig. 14. Due to the random orientation of particles, the torques along the x'
691 and y' axes ($T_{x'}$ and $T_{y'}$) exhibit mean values close to zero. However, the torque component along the
692 z' axis ($T_{z'}$), which governs particle flipping, remains consistently non-negligible. $T_{z'}$ exhibits a

693 negative mean value follows a trend similar to that of the lift force. At the symmetric orientations of
694 $\theta=0^\circ$ and $\theta=90^\circ$, the average torque is zero, indicating no net rotational tendency due to the balanced
695 torque field. However, for intermediate orientations, particles experience non-zero torque arising
696 from asymmetric flow structures. Specifically, at $\theta=45^\circ$, elongated particles tend to align their long
697 axis perpendicular to the flow direction, resulting in a maximum flipping torque driven by fluid inertia.

698 At a high $Re=2000$ and $\varphi=0.2$, the peak torque occurs at $\theta=45^\circ$, reaching a value of 87.418. This
699 is significantly greater than the corresponding value of 0.4668 observed at $\varphi=0.05$ under the same Re
700 condition, as illustrated in Fig. 14(c) and (f). This pronounced increase can be attributed to two
701 primary factors. First, a higher Re enhances inertial forces, leading to more pronounced asymmetry
702 in pressure distribution and greater wake deflection around inclined particles, thereby increasing the
703 resulting hydrodynamic torque. Second, in dense particulate systems, the presence of neighboring
704 particles disrupts the local flow symmetry around each particle, amplifying the asymmetry and
705 intensifying the induced torque. These coupled effects are especially evident at higher φ , emphasizing
706 the non-negligible role of torque under such conditions. Similar findings were also reported in Refs.
707 [43, 44] in studies conducted at lower Re ($Re \leq 300$), supporting the validity of the present observations.

708

709

Fig. 14. Variation of F_T with θ for cylindrical particles at Re and φ

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713

In current studies of particle laden suspensions, the influence of neighboring particles on hydrodynamic torque has not been fully considered. However, Mema et al. [75] emphasized that the omission of such interactions may hinder the accurate understanding of the rotational dynamics of non-spherical particles.

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718

Given the similarity between the variation trends of torque and lift with respect to the incidence angle, this study retains the trigonometric form $\sin\theta\cos\theta$ to capture the orientation dependence. A novel torque correlation model was developed as a function of Re , φ , and θ , as shown in Eq. (27)–(29). This model is also used to compute the average torque experienced by particles in the suspension system.

719

$$H = (1 + d_1 Re + d_2 \varphi + d_2 \sin(\theta) \cos(\theta)) / (d_4 + d_5 Re + d_6 \varphi + d_7 \sin(\theta) \cos(\theta)) \quad (27)$$

720

$$G = (e_1 - \varphi)^2 - (1 / (e_2 - \varphi)^3) \quad (28)$$

721

$$F_{T,\theta} = H * G \quad (29)$$

722

723 To obtain the optimal fitting parameters for the novel proposed torque model, a genetic algorithm
 724 was employed, involving thousands of optimization iterations. The final set of fitted coefficients is
 725 presented in Table 8.

726 Table 8 Correlation fitting optimized coefficients used in F_T

i	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
d_i	10.1805	476.5676	1295.9335	85.5776	-0.0002	34.0519	-123.4843
e_i	-0.1567	1.1272					

727 The torque curves predicted by the novel developed model are illustrated in Fig. 15,
 728 demonstrating strong agreement with the IBM-PR-DNS simulation results. Quantitative comparison
 729 indicates that the average relative error of the model is 6.27%, with a root mean square error (RMSE)
 730 of 0.474, a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.9991, and a median relative error of 7.95%. Although
 731 the torque model exhibits slightly greater data scatter compared to the drag and lift models, the overall
 732 fit remains satisfactory. No systematic overprediction or underprediction is observed, indicating that
 733 the model effectively captures the primary trends of torque variation with φ , θ , and Re .

734

735

Fig. 15. Comparison between IBM-PR-DNS torque data and the correlation of the novel model.

736

Symbol: IBM-PR-DNS data; Dashed line: correlation prediction

737

738

3.4 Comparison with existing literature

739

The multiparticle force model proposed in this study is specifically developed for suspended

740

systems of cylindrical particles with $Ar=2.5$. It is applicable under flow conditions with $10 \leq Re \leq 2000$

741

and $0.05 \leq \varphi \leq 0.2$. The model explicitly accounts for the random orientation of particles within the

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suspension, with incidence angles θ ranging from 0° to 90° , enabling accurate prediction of

743

hydrodynamic forces acting on particles across a wide range of spatial orientations.

744

Since current literature lacks effective correlations for predicting lift and torque in particle

745

suspension systems, we quantitatively evaluated the accuracy of the proposed novel drag model by

746

comparing its predictions with several representative drag force correlations. For instance, He and

747 Tafti [41] developed a drag model for randomly suspended ellipsoidal particles with $Ar=0.25$,
748 applicable for $10 \leq Re \leq 200$ and $0.1 \leq \varphi \leq 0.35$. Chen [46] proposed a model for cubic particles with
749 $Ar=1$ and φ between 0.1 and 0.45, targeting lower Reynolds numbers ($Re < 200$). Cao and Tafti [44]
750 studied disk-like particles with $Ar=0.25$ and proposed a sinusoidal correction function based on
751 incidence angles, applicable for $\varphi \leq 0.3$ and $10 \leq Re \leq 300$.

752 As illustrated in Fig. 16(a), when comparing drag predictions under the same conditions ($Ar=$
753 2.5 , $\varphi=0.1$), significant discrepancies are observed between our cylindrical particle model and the
754 ellipsoid based correlation, with the average relative error increasing from 22.43% at $Re=10$ to 52.81%
755 at $Re=100$. This highlights the importance of particle shape in accurate drag prediction.

756 To further investigate the influence of Re on the predictive performance of different models,
757 Fig.16(b) compares the present correlation with several representative drag models for non-spherical
758 particles under two solid volume fractions ($\varphi=0.1$ and $\varphi=0.2$). The results clearly show that
759 differences in particle shape lead to significant variations in both the predicted drag magnitude and
760 its trend with increasing Re .

761 Using the present model as a baseline, the drag predicted for cubic particles—characterized by
762 sharp edges and relatively weak flow separation—is consistently lower, with a maximum relative
763 error of 23.03% observed at $\varphi=0.2$ and $Re=200$. In contrast, disk-shaped particles exhibit the highest
764 drag due to their large frontal area facing the flow, with a maximum relative error of 17.65% under
765 the same conditions.

766 The proposed novel drag model is specifically developed for cylindrical biomass particles with
767 a moderate aspect ratio of $Ar=2.5$, whose hydrodynamic behavior falls between that of cubes and flat
768 disks. More importantly, the model covers a broader Re range, extending from laminar to transitional
769 regimes (up to $Re=2000$), making it particularly suitable for capturing the drag characteristics of

770 typical cylindrical biomass particles like straw in the various flow conditions. This broad applicability
 771 highlights its superior generalizability compared to existing models that are limited to specific particle
 772 shapes.

773

774

775 Fig. 16. Comparison between the novel F_D correlation and the existing literature models

776 (a) Comparison of cylindrical and ellipsoidal particles at $Ar=2.5$ and $\phi=0.1$;

777 solid lines represent $Re=10$, dashed lines represent $Re=100$

778 (b) Variation with Re for $Ar=1$ cube, $Ar=2.5$ cylinder, and $Ar=0.25$ disk-shaped particles

779 To verify the robustness of the model, an independent test case was conducted at $Re=600$ and

780 $\phi=0.18$ using IBM-PR-DNS results as reference. As list in Table 9, the predicted drag, lift, and torque

781 values across different incidence angles closely matched the simulation results, with an average

782 relative error of only 4.03% and a maximum error below 9%. This confirms the model's high accuracy

783 and strong generalization capability under random flow conditions.

784 In summary, the proposed correlation outperforms existing models in terms of accuracy,

785 applicability, and sensitivity to particle orientation. It provides a reliable framework for predicting

786 forces on cylindrical biomass particles in multiphase systems, supporting more accurate simulations

787 in fluidization, biomass combustion, and other gas-solid flow applications.

788

789

Table 9 Comparison of IBM-PR-DNS and novel model correlations ($Ar=2.5$, $\varphi=0.18$, $Re=600$)

θ ($^{\circ}$)	F_D			F_L			F_T		
	IBM-PR- DNS	Correlation	$R^*(\%)$	IBM- PR-DNS	Correlation	$R^{**}(\%)$	IBM- PR-DNS	Correlation	$R^{**}(\%)$
5	96.158	97.146	1.027	3.421	3.695	8.005	7.495	7.674	2.395
25	93.257	95.028	1.899	14.954	16.286	8.910	16.701	16.012	4.125
45	81.574	84.491	3.576	20.296	21.211	4.507	23.923	24.850	3.877
65	69.821	67.223	3.721	15.287	16.150	5.643	16.417	15.848	3.467
85	54.339	55.615	2.348	3.719	3.486	6.271	7.547	7.599	0.695

790

791 **4. Conclusion**

792 This study employed an immersed boundary method particle resolved direct numerical
793 simulation (IBM-PR-DNS) to investigate the hydrodynamic behavior of cylindrical biomass particles
794 with an aspect ratio of $Ar=2.5$ suspended in fluid media. Simulations covered a wide range of
795 Reynolds numbers ($Re \leq 2000$), solid volume fractions ($0.05 \leq \varphi \leq 0.2$), and particle incidence angles
796 ($0^{\circ} \leq \theta \leq 90^{\circ}$). Based on the numerical data, novel predictive models were developed for drag, lift, and
797 torque, and their accuracy was validated against existing correlations in the literature. The main
798 conclusions are as follows:

799 1) At a low solid volume fraction ($\varphi=0.05$), the flow remains relatively uniform with weak inter-
800 particle interference, and the force distribution approximates a linear superposition. As φ increases to
801 0.2, the flow becomes significantly more heterogeneous, with the formation of high-velocity channels
802 and low-speed recirculation zones, leading to strong local force variation on particles.

803 2) Drag force exhibits a distinct nonlinear dependence on the incidence angles, particularly at
804 high Reynolds numbers. For example, at $Re=2000$ and $\varphi=0.2$, the drag decreases by up to 46.33% as
805 θ increases from 5° to 85° . Both lift and torque coefficients are more sensitive to θ and tend to peak
806 around $\theta \approx 45^{\circ}$, indicating the strong dependence of non-spherical particle dynamics on orientation
807 and wake asymmetry. Their magnitudes grow significantly with increasing Re and φ .

808 3) The novel proposed models demonstrate excellent accuracy, with root mean square errors

809 (RMSE) of 0.463 (drag), 0.131 (lift), and 0.474 (torque), and average relative errors below 4.39%,
810 4.98%, and 6.27%, respectively. All models yield R^2 values above 0.9991, and the maximum median
811 relative error is 7.95%.

812 4) Comparative analysis with existing models—including those for ellipsoids (He and Tafti),
813 cubes (Chen), and disks (Cao and Tafti)—reveals that the proposed drag correlation outperforms
814 others under randomly oriented particle suspensions. It better captures the force behavior of
815 cylindrical biomass particles representative of real condition co-firing applications.

816 The proposed force correlation models offer a robust and accurate tool for computational fluid
817 dynamics (CFD) simulations of biomass co-firing, fluidized bed combustion, and gas-solid
818 multiphase flow. However, it should be noted that these correlations were derived based on isothermal,
819 incompressible flow conditions and a fixed particle configuration. As non-spherical biomass particles
820 are often utilized in high-temperature combustion zones, thermal effects—such as temperature-
821 induced variations in fluid viscosity, density, and particle properties—can significantly affect the
822 hydrodynamic forces and motion behavior. Therefore, future work will incorporate thermally coupled
823 flow simulations to improve the applicability of the models in realistic combustor environments. In
824 addition, we plan to incorporate the force and torque correlations developed in this study into a
825 coupled novel translational-rotational motion model for non-spherical particles, enabling more
826 accurate predictions of particle dynamics under complex flow conditions. Furthermore, since the
827 particle aspect ratio (Ar) greatly influences the flow field, wake structure, and surface pressure
828 distribution, future research will aim to generalize the proposed correlation framework by extending
829 the PR-DNS database to cover a wider range of Ar values and higher solid volume fractions. This
830 will enable the development of more universal drag, lift, and torque models for a broader class of
831 non-spherical particles in engineering applications. Future work will also incorporate experimental

832 methods, such as high-speed Particle Image Velocimetry (PIV), to validate transient force
833 fluctuations and further support the application of our model in realistic engineering scenarios.
834 Moreover, advanced flow topology analysis techniques (e.g., Q-criterion, streamline visualization)
835 will be employed to explore the coupling between wake dynamics and unsteady hydrodynamic forces,
836 providing deeper physical insights into the particle-fluid interactions.

837

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843

844

845 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

846 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
847 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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